

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842

ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

Vol. IV Issue II, February 2024

Monthly Issue

International Circulation

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269

DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433

TIN 293-150-678/ Business Permit No. 8183

San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2300

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DIGITAL LITERACY AND CHALLENGES OF TEACHERS YIZHOU DISTRICT, CHINA

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to investigate the digital literacy degree of junior high school teachers in Yizhou District, Guangxi, China, through the following five (5) dimensions: a) digital awareness, b) digital technical knowledge and skills, c) digital application, d) digital social responsibility, and e) teachers' professional development. The survey results showed that junior high school teachers in Yizhou District had a high degree of digital awareness, digital social responsibility, and professional development, and an average degree of digital technical knowledge and skills and digital application. The overall performance was high.

Moreover, teachers encountered top five (5) challenges: a) insufficient ability to produce their own digital resources, b) difficulty in deeply integrating digital technologies with subjects, c) lack of professional teams to support teachers in using digital technical resources, d) a large number of digital network platforms with complex structures, which take teachers a lot of time to find and sort out, e) innovative application of digital technology resources in teaching.

The findings of this study could serve as a foundation for improving teachers' digital literacy and contribute to the development of education management policies and practices.

Keywords: Digital Literacy, Challenges, Junior high school, Teachers

1. Introduction

Digital literacy is a basic literacy for every citizen in modern society. The *Global Framework of Reference on Digital Literacy Skills* indicates that the aim of improving digital literacy skills is to improve the ability for employment, decent and entrepreneurship. Digital literacy focuses on technology security and the people' ability to properly access, manage, understand, integrate, communicate, evaluate and create information (Law et al., 2018). Goal 4 on quality education of the UN Sustainable Development also targets at increasing the number of people

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who need to improve their skills for employment, decent work and entrepreneurship, especially the percentage of youth and adults who are numerically literate.

In the context of the digital age, the aim of digital literacy improving ultimately is to realize Sustainable Development Goal 4 so as to achieve equitable and inclusive quality education and create lifelong learning opportunities for all.

In modern times, digital technologies and resources are increasingly being applied to educational scenarios, affecting all aspects of teaching practice and improving the traditional learning experience. Digital technologies and resources are facilitating the digital transformation of education, with the potential to address long-term inequalities in educational opportunity. Digital transformation in the field of education is an indispensable component to construct an educational powerhouse, participate in China's progress towards high-quality education.

The European Commission initiated the DigEuLit project with an aim to develop a European digital literacy framework, which helped educators, trainers and learners have a common understanding of digital literacy and integrated digital literacy into European curricula and educational practices in personal development (Martin & Grudziecki, 2006). Joint Research Center (JRC) of the European Commission proposed the EU Digital Literacy Framework for Education educators (DigCompEdu) in its Policy Science Report to respond to actual needs (Christine, 2017). UNESCO's Development of Teachers' Digital Literacy is concerned with the fact that teachers' digital literacy served as an important factor in the improvement of the quality education in the context of digital transformation, which has effectively responded to the challenges of digital technologies, while improving teachers' digital literacy to safeguard the development of students' digital literacy and to plug the digital gap (Kong & Wang, 2023).

The Norwegian Centre for ICT in Education (2017) published *Professional Digital Competence Framework for Teachers*, which aimed to improve the competence and development of teachers' professions as well as to improve teachers' educational quality in the digital context.

The Education and Training Foundation (2019) in the UK published *Digital Teaching for Professional Framework*. The framework guided teachers in utilizing effective pedagogy to improve teaching and learning and support teacher professional development through digital technology.

China's Ministry of Education (2022) released *Framework of Digital Literacy for Teachers*, which constructed a framework of teacher digital literacy through

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five (5) dimensions: a) digital awareness, b) digital technical knowledge and skills, c) digital application, d) digital social responsibility, and e) teachers' professional development, which provides a reference for training and evaluation of digital literacy of Chinese teachers.

In nearly 10 years, more and more scholars in China have begun to focus on studying digital literacy. Through literature analysis of CNKI, it was found that the current researches mainly focused on the connotation of digital literacy, educational content and interpretation of foreign educational policies of digital literacy, and the research objects mainly focused on citizens, college teachers, library librarians, etc. (Chen, 2023; Quan, 2022).

In order to improve teachers' digital literacy in Yizhou District, it is necessary to investigate and analyze the current situation of teachers in order to introduce targeted policies and make specific action plans to help teachers solve the challenges they countered. Combined with the actual situation of the digital transformation of education in Yizhou District, it is of practical significance to study the actual situation related to the digital literacy of junior high school teachers in Yizhou District and identify the challenges encountered by teachers.

Besides, the term "digital literacy" has been demonstrated in various academic documents, national policy documents and other materials in terms of digital skills, digital competence, digital capability, etc., but it is not unified (Wu, 2023). However, they all emphasize the attitude, knowledge, ability, moral awareness and so on while solving problems in the digital age in terms of digital technology skills. In this study, the researcher considered them equal to digital literacy.

2. Method

This study adapted a descriptive survey, and the evaluation part of the questionnaire was designed to be detailed in five (5) dimensions under the framework of Chinese teachers' digital literacy: a) digital awareness, b) digital technical knowledge and skills, c) digital application, d) digital social responsibility and e) teachers' professional development. The research collected and analyzed data from three perspectives: teachers' self-evaluation, school-level leaders' evaluation of teachers, and teachers' evaluation of other teachers in their school. The comprehensive results described the situation of teachers' digital literacy.

This study employed quantitative research to achieve the results of the study. Quantitative research means that the researcher subdivides the reality into understandable variables that can be observed and tested, and then draws

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conclusions through mathematical analysis after a series of observations and data collection (Almalki, 2016; Timmaz et al. 2022). The use of triangulation in research can enrich the research content, which helps to improve the credibility and validity of the research process and increase researchers' confidence in the research results (Heale & Forbes, D.2013). One of the most common studies using triangulation involved having two or more groups of data collected using the same method. The combination of two or more results could provide a more comprehensive picture than either data alone (Noble & Heale, 2019; Bans-Akutey & Tiimub 2021).

The researcher conducted the study on the digital literacy of the subject teachers in twenty-three (23) junior high schools in Yizhou District during the 2023-2024 school year. This study used convenient sample sampling to identify twenty-three (23) school-level leaders and two hundred and ninety-nine (299) teachers. Cronbach Alpha are used to measure the reliability of the item in the questionnaire. The coefficient was computed and recorded as 0.958, which meant the questionnaire was highly reliable. And the study's questionnaire was validated by five (5) qualified experts.

3. Results and Discussions

3.1 Digital literacy

The degree of teachers' digital literacy affects whether they adapt to the digital transformation and educational development. This survey questionnaire was based and adapted from the teachers' digital literacy of China framework. This survey questionnaire was based and adapted from the teachers' digital literacy of China framework. It included the following five (5) dimensions: a) digital awareness, b) digital technical knowledge and skills, c) digital application, d) digital social responsibility, and e) teachers' professional development.

Table 1
Summary of Digital Literacy of the Teachers

Digital literacy	Teachers self-evaluation		School-level leaders evaluation of teachers		Peers' evaluation		WM	VD
	M	VD	M	VD	M	VD		
Digital awareness	3.51	H	3.52	H	3.56	H	3.53	H

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Digital technical knowledge and skills	3.31	A	3.30	A	3.48	A	3.36	A
Digital application	3.27	A	3.43	A	3.51	H	3.40	A
Digital social responsibility	4.20	H	4.28	H	4.04	H	4.18	H
Teachers' professional development	3.52	H	3.43	A	3.61	H	3.52	H
GRAND MEAN	3.56	H	3.59	H	3.64	H	3.60	H

Legend: (5) 4.51 – 5.00 **VH**-Very High; (4)3.51 - 4.50 **H**-High; (3) 2.51 – 3.50 **A**-Average; (2) 1.51 - 2.50 **L**-Low; (1) 1.0-

1.50 **VL**-Very Low;

M-MEAN **VD**-Verbal Description **WM**-Weighted Mean

According to Table 1, the dimension of digital awareness, the mean of teachers' self-evaluation was 3.51, and the verbal description was *High (H)*; the grand mean of school-level leaders' evaluation was 3.52, and the mean of peers' evaluation was 3.56, and the verbal description was *High (H)*; the grand mean of the three (3) groups of data was 3.53, with verbal description as *High (H)*. It shows that in the dimension of digital awareness, teachers have a high degree of understanding and cognition, and actively learn and carry out digital applications. In this respect, their performance is *High (H)*.

Additionally, Chen (2023) found that teachers had a high awareness of digitalization and a clear understanding of digitalization when teachers' digital literacy was evaluated and analyzed in some regions of China. Digital awareness is a prerequisite for teachers to effectively apply digital technology resources to implement teaching activities and promote their own development. The higher the degree of digitization, the more it can promote the teaching innovation and professional ability growth of teachers. This supports the findings of this study that teachers generally perform to a high degree in the dimension of digital awareness.

The second dimension of digital technical knowledge and skills, the grand mean of teachers' self-evaluation was 3.31, and the verbal description was *Average (A)*; the mean of school-level leaders' evaluation was 3.30, and the grand mean of peers' evaluation was 3.48, with the verbal description as *Average (A)*; the grand mean of the three (3) groups of data was 3.36, with the verbal description as *Average (A)*. In terms of digital technical knowledge and skills, the results of the three groups of data show that teachers' understanding and mastery are average, which requires teachers to further understand relevant knowledge and skills.

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Previous researches had shown that it was necessary for teachers to use teaching strategies, and different digital techniques to increase the chance of learning (Yarbro et al, 2016). Digital resources supported the learning and teaching process, and they were useful, attention-grabbing and interesting. Digital resources needed to be introduced into the classroom to enrich the educational environment (Demirkan, 2019).

In the digital application dimension, teachers' self-evaluation got a mean of 3.27, with verbal description as *Average (A)*. School-level leaders gave teachers a mean of 3.43 in this dimension, with verbal description as *Average (A)*, which is consistent with the teachers' self-evaluation. The peers' evaluation had a mean score of 3.51, and verbal description was *High (H)*. The result is higher than school-level leaders' evaluation and the self-evaluation of teachers. The mean score for the three (3) groups of data was 3.40, with verbal description as *Average (A)*. The results show that teachers have a average performance as for the degree of digital application.

Furthermore, the results on the dimension of digital social responsibility show that the mean of teachers' self-evaluation was 4.20, and verbal description was *High (H)*. The mean of the school-level leaders' evaluation was 4.28, and verbal description was *High (H)*. The mean of the peer evaluation was 4.04, and verbal description was *High (H)*. The grand mean of the three (3) groups of data was 4.18, with verbal description as *High (H)*. It shows that teachers demonstrate best practice in digital social responsibility ethics and digital security.

In carrying out digital activities, teachers are able to abide by moral and ethical norms, pay attention to maintaining a positive monitoring network environment, and effectively manage and protect private information and work data (Chen, 2023). Which support existing research findings.

Besides, in items of the dimension of teachers' professional development the mean of teachers' self-evaluation was 3.52, and the verbal description was *High (H)*; the mean of school-level leaders' evaluation was 3.43, with verbal description as *Average (A)*. The mean of peers' evaluation was 3.61, and the verbal description was *High (H)*; the grand mean of the three (3) groups of data was 3.52, with verbal description as *High (H)*. It shows that teachers have a higher degree of performance in utilizing digital technology and resources to apply teachers' professional development dimensions.

Additionally, Mailizar et al., (2022) studied that it was necessary for education stakeholders to provide adequate digital literacy for teachers to ensure their continued participation in future professional development. Teacher digital

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literacy, of which the professional development (PD) had the highest average score and Innovative Education (IE) having the lowest average score (Tzafilkou et al., (2023), consistent with the findings of the current study.

As showed in table 1, the overall situation of digital literacy. Teachers' self-evaluation got a grand mean score of is 3.56, the verbal description was *High (H)*, the school-level leaders gave teachers a grand mean score of 3.59, and verbal description was *High (H)*, the peers' evaluation grand mean score was 3.64 and verbal description was *High (H)*. The grand mean of the three (3) groups of data in the table was 3.52, with verbal description as *High (H)*.

Although the overall digital literacy of junior high school teachers in Yizhou District was shown to be high degree, the two dimensions of digital technical knowledge and skills, and digital application were still average degree. This is due to the current fast development of new digital technologies, teachers do not have enough time and energy to increase their knowledge of digital technologies. Teachers are not able to fully grasp the use of commonly used digital facilities, and problem solutions. In teaching applications, teachers lack digital teaching flexibility and innovation, and digital teaching application skills need to be further improved.

3.2 Challenges

With the requirements of the digital transformation of national education, it is of indispensable value to cultivate and improve teachers' digital literacy. The teachers are still encountering many challenges in the implementation of digital concrete work. The challenges come from both internal and external factors, which affect the implementation of teachers' digital teaching and the improvement of digital literacy.

The researcher summarized 13 items of challenges through literature research and teachers' pre-survey interviews. Table 2 presents the top five (5) challenges encountered by teachers in digital literacy, with more than 50% of respondents' responses.

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Table 2
Challenges Encountered by Teachers

Challenges Encountered	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Insufficient ability to produce their own digital resources.	206	63.98%	1
Difficulty in deeply integrating digital technologies with subjects.	194	60.25%	2
Lack of professional team to support teachers in using digital technology resources.	185	57.45%	3
A large number of digital network platforms with complex structures, which take teachers a lot of time to find and sort out.	184	57.14%	4
Innovative application of digital technology resources in teaching.	173	53.73%	5

The **first challenge** highlighted is that “insufficient ability to produce their own digital resources”. Among the three hundred and twenty-two (322) respondents, two hundred and six (206) responded, with a response rate of 63.98%, and 206 (63.98%) respondents considered it as a challenge. Digital resources made by teachers themselves refers to the re-creation of new forms and new contents of teaching resources by teachers’ using existing digital resources and combining with the actual needs of teaching. This requires teachers to have high innovation ability and high integration ability of digital technology knowledge.

The **second challenge** encountered by teachers is that “difficulty in deeply integrating digital technologies with subjects”. Among the three hundred and twenty-two (322) respondents, one hundred and ninety-four (194) respondents responded, accounting for 60.25%. Different subjects have different teaching objectives and subject characteristics, and teachers need to choose appropriate digital tools and resources to support their own subjects. At the same time, different platforms and subject software have different operating interfaces and system requirements. Teachers need to understand their characteristics and scope of use, so that they can integrate digital technical resources into subjects to ensure the completion of teaching processes and teaching effects (Li, 2021).

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Some teachers simply applied digital technology and lacked deep integration with their subjects (Chen & Kong, 2023). At present, teachers do not have enough understanding of the knowledge and concepts and the mechanism of the application of digital technology, which hinders the deep integration of digital technology and subjects.

The **third challenge**, was responded by 185 respondents and accounting for 57.45%, is that "Lack of professional team to support teachers in using digital technology resources". In daily teaching work, teachers choose and use digital technologies and resources through their own learning and use experience, and the school has no digital technology team to provide support. The reality is that there is no special team support position in the school, and the school has 1-2 information technology teachers to manage digital equipment part-time. Teachers hope to get professional team support when using digital equipment and encountering digital related problems. Besides, for some teachers who adapt to traditional teaching, they are not familiar with or confident in using digital skills and resources, and they will have a certain degree of worry and adaptation difficulties. They need a certain amount of training and help from a team (Li, 2023).

The **fourth challenge** highlighted in table 2 is that "a large number of digital network platforms with complex structures, which take teachers a lot of time to find and sort out.". Among the three hundred and twenty-two (322) respondents, 184 responded to this challenge, accounting for 57.14%. At this stage, smart education platform and excellent curriculum platform that has been built at the national level; Each province also established their own resource platform (such as Air Classroom), operating software (such as Bagui teaching tool); at the social level, there are platform websites developed by companies, social groups or individuals (such as Science Network) and software (such as: Seewo Board V). Although there are many digital technology tools and resources for teachers to choose from, teachers need to spend a lot of time studying, searching and using in the face of a large number of network platforms and massive resources. This situation affects teachers' work efficiency and discourages teachers' enthusiasm for using digital technology resources.

Meanwhile, the **fifth challenge** is that "innovative application of digital technology resources in teaching". Among the 322 respondents, 173 responded, accounting for 53.73%. The daily teaching tasks of teachers are already very tight, and it is a good performance to use existing digital technology resources to carry out teaching. It is difficult to spare time to carry out innovative teaching activities.

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Although teachers often use digital technology resources to constantly innovate teaching modes and improve teaching activities, but their innovative ability is still insufficient at this stage, and they still think that it is a challenge to apply digital technology resources to teaching innovation. Teachers usually need a lot of time to complete the existing teaching tasks, it is difficult to have time to carry out digital innovative teaching. Teachers encountered some challenges of insufficient personalized teaching resources in schools (Wang, 2022).

4. Limitations of the Study

Although this study provides valuable insights into the study of digital literacy among junior high school teachers in Yizhou District, there are some limitations to be acknowledged. First of all, the subject of this study is only for junior high school teachers in Yizhou, Guangxi, which is limited by the actual situation, including the number of samples and the scope.

One-time survey was used in this study. However, digital-literacy cultivation of teachers is a long-term and dynamic development process. One-time survey can only reflect the situation of teachers' digital literacy at a certain point in time, but can not reflect the development process of digital literacy. Therefore, future research can make up for this limitation through process evaluation.

5. Conclusions

The following conclusions based on the summary of results and findings were drawn.

Based on the evaluation of the current state of teachers' digital literacy, the three dimensions of digital awareness, digital social responsibility and teachers' professional development reached a high degree. This indicates a high degree of active integration of teachers into digitized education and teaching, the assumption of responsibility for the social identity of teachers in digitized contexts, and the use of digitized approaches and resources by teachers to improve their own development. But teachers can still be strengthened in this area to reach the highest level of Very high. Compared to the above dimensions, the degree of the two dimensions of teachers' digital technical knowledge and skills, and digital application are at the average degree. It shows that there are deficiencies in teachers' own digital knowledge and skills as well as in their ability to use digital technologies and resources to solve practical problems in teaching and learning, and that stakeholders need to pay attention to teachers' improvement in these two areas.

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Moreover, participants have identified challenges to teachers' digital literacy. The Top 5 challenges responded to by the respondents focused on these two dimensions of teachers' digital technical skills knowledge and skills and digital applications. The challenges encountered by teachers focus on the practices related to digital teaching and learning, and teachers need the support of external people and environments, as well as their own competencies to cope with them.

As a result of the findings, digital literacy of teachers in terms of the dimensions: digital technical knowledge and skills and digital application, the degree were both in average degree. Teachers' use of digital technology and resources to solve practical teaching problems is not enough and all stakeholders need to pay attention to the improvement of teachers in these two areas.

Teachers need to improve digital teaching and learning methods to improve the aspects of digital literacy weaknesses. Teachers need to change the traditional classroom teaching mode, create diversified teaching methods and assessment methods. Schools adjust the content and assessment focus of digital literacy evaluation for teachers in a timely manner, emphasizing the school's focus on the mastery of teachers' technical knowledge and skills in digital technology, the application of digital teaching, and the importance of digital innovation.

6. Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, the recommendations are drawn as following:

1. Education department at local District and schools should organize more digital related activities or competitions, encouraging teachers to actively learn and apply digital teaching technology, and encouraging teachers to continuously improve their own digital teaching level and ability, and further improve teaching quality.

2. The schools should combine the research results with the actual situation of the school, take the problems as a guide, and formulate personalized and differentiated training for teachers in different disciplines.

3. Researchers strongly suggest that teachers should conduct in-depth research and continue to improve their digital social responsibility, digital awareness, and teachers' professional development. Although the grand mean scores of teachers in these three (3) areas have reached a high level, there is still a gap from the highest standards. Stakeholders are expected to support teachers' sustainable development in these areas.

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4. Teachers should adhere to the lifelong learning concept and constantly learn new digital technical knowledge and skills to adapt to the changing educational environment. Teachers should try to keep pace with the times in digital changes and adapt to new technological changes and changes in educational models.

5. Teachers should manage their time well, make full use of their spare time and participate in some training and workshops aimed at digital innovation independently. These courses can enable teachers to learn more teaching methods and techniques, so as to better solve practical problems in teaching.

6. Future researchers, in combination with the actual situation in their region, will develop a tool to evaluate the normalization of teachers' digital literacy, collect and record teachers' digital related data, and realize the process of tracking evaluation and feedback in time.

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DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10643806

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International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT
Multidisciplinary e-Publication
Volume IV, Issue II (Feb. 2024)/ International Circulation
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

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